

A Novel Performance-Optimized Chaotic Mapping Technique for Secure and Compressed Image Transmission

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Abstract- Secure communication and computing is the vital requirement of the day as global networks and information systems are expanding like the big bang theory of the universe. People have started treating information as an asset. The information asset needs to be secured from attacks. Everything in the world is being upgraded to electronic communication and this requires protection against data fraud. Information has chosen different media like text, image, audio, video and multimedia for its existence. Cryptography is the science which provides techniques for securing information over network. Network security is the process of taking physical and software measures to protect underlying infrastructure. This paper introduces cryptography, chaotic cryptography, its computational power in image security. It proposes new sealion algorithm to increase the computational power of cryptographic algorithms. It also verifies the efficiency of proposed algorithm against benchmarks set for the security of images over network.

Keywords – Cryptography, Chaotic Cryptography, Image Security, Network Security, Secure Communication.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Medical Infrastructure of the world is growing along with scientific and technical inventions. In order to perform the diagnosis, the medical experts require the patient's data, which can be in the form of text, image, or video. Currently, clinicians widely adopt biomedical images for diagnosis because these images are considered a source of rich medical information. These medical images are obtained using various imaging technologies such as radiographs, ultrasound, X-ray, Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI), Computed Tomography (CT), Photoacoustic Imaging and many others.

Telemedicine and Remote Health Monitoring Systems are widely adopted where biomedical images are transmitted over the public network to different locations for expert analysis and decision.

As private data have to be transmitted over public networks, they suffer from the severe problem of intercepting, tampering and destroying. Moreover, intruders can steal or modify the data while transmitting these data over a communication channel. And also, Dicom images contain sensitive data and occupy huge storage space in memory. They require large bandwidth for transmission over the network. So, in these communications, faster data transmission is required while ensuring successful and secure data transmission.

Researchers have developed and proposed several techniques to address bandwidth requirements and security issues of dicom images over the network. Image Compression is the solution suggested by the research to reduce bandwidth requirement and image encryption is adopted to secure images from modification and theft.

To address the challenges present in the existing systems, research has been taken up to develop an efficient system to perform compression and encryption operation of Dicom images. Image compression is achieved by lossless Huffman Coding compression algorithm by using Discrete Wavelet transform in Linear Predictive Coding and Encryption is carried out by adopting chaotic maps using Average Fitness based SeaLion optimization algorithm

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Recently, many techniques have been designed and developed to provide security to the Dicom images over the network in the telemedicine domain.

Zhang et al.[1] developed a joint scheme for image compression and encryption based on compressive sensing and Fourier transform. This scheme used a chaos system and two-dimensional fractional Fourier transform (2D- FRT) to perform the encryption.

Yu et al.[2] have projected a novel Image Encryption Algorithm (IEA) based on the Phase Truncated Short Time

Fractional Fourier Transform PTSTFrFT) and the Hyper Chaotic System(H-CS). The experimental evaluation of the projected model revealed better keyspace and high sensitivity. Zhang et al.[3] developed a novel method for lossless image encryption based on set partitioning in hierarchical trees and cellular automata. The encryption method embedded the encryption into the compression process. A small part of the data is encrypted quickly while maintaining the good coding characteristics of set partitioning in hierarchical trees (SPIHT).

Yang et al.[4] developed a fractional-order memristive band-pass filter (BPF).The chaotic circuit was constructed based on BPF chaotic circuit and fractional definition. The attractor and fractal characteristics were analysed through phase diagrams and time domain response diagrams. In addition, the randomness of the chaotic pseudo-random sequences was tested through NIST SP800–22 and correlation of sequence.

Romi Fadillah Rahmat et al. [5] adopted Huffman Coding Technique, considering the Bit Frequency Distribution [BFD] as an alternative to standard Lossless JPEG2000 Compression for DICOM files in open PAC settings. The result was that the proposed method generated space-saving of 72.98% with 1:3.7010 compression ratios.

Shakir et al.[6] developed a new method of reliable image encryption, which combined the Haar wavelet transform with the Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) and pixel shuffling based on a chaotic logistic map. In the proposed method, the Haar wavelet transform was calculated from the original image.The approximation part (LL) was then encrypted using the AES algorithm to create the image diffusion.

Nematzadeh et al.[7] adopted an optimization scheme and presented a modified genetic algorithm and coupled map lattices for medical image encryption. The researcher applied coupled map lattice to obtain the secure cipher images, which were used as the initial population for the genetic algorithm

Thoms et al.[8] have introduced ChaosNet as a new IEA based on CKC-NN. The primary objective of CKC-NN is to integrate the roadside units of ITSs. The Lorenz chaotic system and the KCFF-NN were utilized for the encryption process. Further, the resultants from the acquired cryptanalysis exhibited substantial mixing properties and increased information entropy.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The proposed work focuses on improving the telemedicine domain by developing a new crypto compression technique to reduce bandwidth consumption and storage space consumption and protect Dicom images in the public network from modification, eavesdropping, and unauthorized access. For these aspects, hybrid compression and encryption techniques are presented.

The first phase proposes an Optimized two-dimensional chaotic mapping for encrypting the Dicom image. The initial chaotic sequence (CS) parameters were fine-tuned with a new optimization algorithm, the Average Fitness based- SeaLion Algorithm (AF-SL_nO). The proposed AF-SL_nO has maximized the “Information Entropy”. Consequently, the most favorable initial parameters for the chaotic sequence were evaluated.

The second phase presents a combined approach for data compression to reduce the storage and bandwidth requirement and encryption to maintain security. The compression scheme is based on the hybrid approach of Discrete Wavelet Transform using Linear Predictive Coding and Huffman coding. The encryption scheme is based on the confusion and diffusion framework using chaotic sequence supported by the AF-SeaLion algorithm.

The proposed work is depicted by the architecture diagrams.

Figure 1: Block Diagram of the proposed Compression-Encryption Technique

Figure 2: Pixel positions after Permutation & Diffusion Process

Figure 3: Block Diagram of the proposed Decryption-Decompression Technique

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The proposed Dicom Image Compression and Encryption model is implemented in MATLAB R2021a and the results acquired are noted.

Sample Data Set

The dataset for Computed Tomography (CT) and Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) images are downloaded from <https://www.osirix-viewer.com>

And Ultrasound images are downloaded from the website.

<https://www.ultrasoundcases.info/cases/abdomen-and-etropéritoneum/>

Figure 4: Sample Dataset of CT, Ultrasound and MRI Images

Result Analysis

The performance of the proposed approach is measured in terms of standard performance metrics like Histogram Analysis, Entropy, Peak Signal to Noise Ratio (PSNR), Mean Square Error (MSE), Structural Similarity Index (SSIM) and

Auto Correlation Analysis. The Differential Analysis is carried out by the Number of Pixel Change Rate (NPCR) and Unified Average Changing Intensity (UACI), which measures the strength of the compressed-encrypted image against modification in the public network.

PSNR, MSE and SSIM Analysis

Table 1 shows the comparative analysis of PSNR, MSE and SSIM for the Image Compression and Encryption scheme. The proposed approach is tested for Ultrasound, CT and MRI images and the obtained results in terms of PSNR, MSE and SSIM are noted and compared with existing traditional approaches. The results show that PSNR value of 47.1319 is achieved for Ultrasound images, 47%, 28% and 26% higher than SPIHT, DWT, and DCT approaches, respectively.

Table 1: Comparative Analysis of Image Compression

Images	Technique	PSNR (dB)	MSE	SSIM
Ultrasound	SPIHT	31.8378	42.5892	0.768457
	DWT	37.2111	12.3586	0.84581
	DCT	37.502427	11.5568	0.8587
	Proposed	47.13192	1.2586	0.95667
MRI	SPIHT	36.5017	14.5513	0.752314
	DWT	34.8624	21.2243	0.786128
	DCT	32.5415	36.2178	0.89014
	Proposed	44.0333	2.5689	0.983516
C T	SPIHT	34.73046	21.8793	0.755633
	DWT	33.005	32.5516	0.798745
	DCT	35.07131	20.2278	0.845519
	Proposed	43.048	3.2231	0.985941

Histogram Analysis

The histogram analysis of any image illustrates the graphical representation of tone distribution in any given digital image. The difference between the histogram of original and encrypted images shows better cryptography. Table 2 depicts the histogram analysis of image encryption. It is incurred from table 2 that the histogram of the original and encrypted image is very different, indicating good encryption. Furthermore, the histogram of the decrypted image and the original image are almost identical, indicating that the proposed encryption mechanism has good reconstruction quality.

Table 2: Histogram Analysis (a) Original Image (b) Histogram of original Image (c) Cipher Image (d) Histogram of Cipher Image (e) Decrypted Image (f) Histogram of Decrypted Image Table 2(a): Histogram Analysis of MRI Images

Table 2(c): Histogram Analysis of CT Images

Information Entropy Analysis

The Information Entropy Analysis is presented for the considered different modalities of images. The entropy of the presented work and existing work is shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Information Entropy Analysis of Ultrasound, CT and MRI Images

Image modalities	Methods	Images				
		1	2	3	4	5
Ultrasound	Standard	7.951	7.956	7.956	7.958	7.964
	Adaptive GWO [10]	7.965	7.967	7.965	7.967	7.966
	GA[13]	7.968	7.964	7.967	7.965	7.964
	GWO[12]	7.966	7.965	7.965	7.964	7.965
	Proposed	7.986	7.986	7.97	9.985	7.982

CT	Standard	7.959	7.955	7.962	7.957	7.95
	GWO[12]	7.967	7.966	7.964	7.966	7.965
	GA[13]	7.966	7.967	7.966	7.965	7.964
	Adaptive GWO [10]	7.967	7.968	7.968	7.968	7.968
	Proposed	7.986	9.976	7.988	7.991	7.982
MRI	Standard	7.951	7.956	7.951	7.952	7.951
	GWO[12]	7.967	7.966	7.965	7.964	7.965
	GA[13]	7.966	7.965	7.967	7.969	7.965
	Adaptive GWO [10]	7.968	7.967	7.965	7.967	7.967
	Proposed	7.982	7.995	7.991	7.986	7.979

On observing the entropy of the ultrasonic image, the presented work achieves the highest entropy in all images. Further, for the third image, the entropy of the presented work is 0.12%, 0.007%, 0.023%, 0.017% better than the existing works like standard, GWO, WO, and Adaptive GWO, respectively. Then, in the case of CT images, the highest entropy (7.968) is achieved by the presented work at the fifth image, and it is 0.14%, 0.05%, 0.007%, and 0.05% better than the extant models like standard, GWO, GWO, WO, and Adaptive GWO respectively. Further, in the case of MRI images, the entropy of the presented work for the fourth image is 7.986, while the entropy of standard, GWO, WO, and adaptive GWO is 7.952, 7.964, 7.969 and 7.967, respectively. Thus, from the overall

evaluation, it is evident that the presented work shows the highest entropy value and hence reaches the objective.

Differential Analysis

Generally, the image encryption schemes are sensitive to the changes in the plain images, i.e. minor change in the plain image affects the encryption performance. This analysis uses the number of pixels change rate (NPCR) and the unified average changing intensity (UACI). Table 4 shows the comparative analysis of NPCR and UACI. The obtained performance is compared with the existing methods like Standard, Genetic Algorithm and Adaptive Grey Wolf Algorithm.

Table 4: NPCR and UACI Analysis

Image modalities	Methods	NPCR					UACI				
		1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5
Ultrasound	Standard	99.634	99.683	99.536	99.39	99.609	12.207	12.451	12.427	12.793	12.891
	GA[13]	99.683	99.683	99.561	99.487	99.585	12.085	12.769	13.501	12.598	13.745
	GWO[12]	99.756	99.634	99.609	99.487	99.707	12.207	13.281	12.28	12.329	11.23
	Adaptive GWO [10]	99.561	99.463	99.658	99.756	99.634	12.524	12.744	12.891	11.572	13.403
	Proposed	99.765	99.821	99.863	99.891	99.875	14.251	13.41	14.251	13.335	14.502
CT	Standard	99.512	99.585	99.536	99.39	99.609	12.354	12.891	12.427	12.793	12.891
	GA[13]	99.634	99.78	99.561	99.487	99.585	12.207	12.28	13.501	12.598	13.745
	GWO[12]	99.39	99.634	99.609	99.487	99.707	12.72	12.744	12.28	12.329	11.23
	Adaptive GWO [10]	99.731	99.536	99.658	99.756	99.634	12.891	12.915	12.891	11.572	13.403
	Proposed	99.863	99.962	99.823	99.864	99.892	12.912	13.251	12.956	13.208	14.551
MRI	Standard	99.634	99.805	99.536	99.39	99.609	14.038	13.647	12.427	12.793	12.891
	GA[13]	99.512	99.683	99.561	99.487	99.585	12.744	12.744	13.501	12.598	13.745
	GWO[12]	99.609	99.658	99.609	99.487	99.707	12.231	11.914	12.28	12.329	11.23
	Adaptive GWO [10]	99.805	99.78	99.658	99.756	99.634	13.062	12.793	12.891	11.572	13.403
	Proposed	99.127	99.868	99.921	99.789	99.863	14.587	14.621	13.251	12.881	13.852

Compression Ratio

The Compression Ratio (CR) measures the amount of data compression occurred. The compression rate achieved by the proposed algorithm is presented in Table 5. The compression rate evaluation of the proposed algorithm evidently shows that

the bandwidth requirement and storage space requirement for the dicom images is reduced to 88% for Ultrasound Images, 90% for CT images and 92% for MRI images.

Table 5: Compression Ratio Analysis

Ultrasound Image		CT Image		MRI Image	
Image	Compression Ratio	Image	Compression Ratio	Image	Compression Ratio
Image1	87.5%	Image1	91.74%	Image1	92.17%
Image2	88.09%	Image2	90.85%	Image2	93.01%
Image3	88.76%	Image3	90.88%	Image3	92.49%
Image4	88.23%	Image4	91.03%	Image4	92.06%
Image5	88.78%	Image5	91.74%	Image5	92.91%

Execution Time

The time required to perform the proposed compression and encryption operation is noted. Table 6 shows the time taken for the compression-encryption operation.

The compression ratio achieved by the proposed algorithm is 88% for Ultrasound Images, 90% for CT images and 92% for MRI images contributing to the reduction of storage space and bandwidth requirements.

Table 6: Time consumption to Compress & Encrypt

Ultrasound Image		CT Image		MRI Image	
Image	Execution Time (in Secs)	Image	Execution Time (in Secs)	Image	Execution Time (in Secs)
Image 1	2.1384	Image1	0.924	Image 1	0.7185
Image 2	2.5684	Image2	0.6643	Image 2	0.7082
Image 3	3.1258	Image3	0.7979	Image 3	0.7109
Image 4	2.0986	Image4	0.7845	Image 4	0.745
Image 5	2.1945	Image5	0.9023	Image 5	0.7537

FUTURE DIRECTIONS

In future, Compression and Encryption can be implemented with a better simulator by considering noise models. Artificial Intelligence and Cloud Storage. For further analysis, network properties may be considered for the adequate security of the images. The work may be enhanced by considering ROI based compression techniques, Deep Learning and Blockchain Technology.

REFERENCES

- Zhang, M., Tong, X. J., Liu, J., Wang, Z., Liu, J., Liu, B., & Ma, J. (2020), "Image Compression and Encryption Scheme Based on Compressive Sensing and Fourier Transform". IEEE Access, 8, 40838-40849.
- Cha-Cha Yu, Nan-Run Zhou, Li-Hua Gong, Zhe Nie (2020), "Optical image encryption algorithm based on phase-truncated short-time fractional Fourier transform and hyper-chaotic system", Optics and Lasers in Engineering, vol.124.
- Zhang, H., Wang, X. Q., Sun, Y. J. & Wang, X. Y (2020), "A novel method for lossless image compression and encryption based on LWT, SPIHT and cellular automata. Signal Processing." Image Communication, 84, 115829.
- Yang, F., Mou, J., Sun, K., & Chu, R.(2020), "Lossless image compression-encryption algorithm based on bp neural network and chaotic system." Multimedia Tools and Applications, 79(27), 19963-19992.

IV. CONCLUSION

The proposed Crypto Compression algorithm has resulted in increased PSNR value. It is 48%, 20% and 23% more in Ultrasound, CT and MRI images with respect to SPIHT, DWT and DCT methods respectively. Even at the receiving end, the recovered image is almost identical to the original image by inverse operations like decryption and decoding. The structural similarity index for the recovered image is 0.985, which is very near to the benchmark value of 1, which indicate that the image at the destination is almost the same as the image at the sending entity.

5. Romi Fadillah Rahmat (2019), "Analysis of DICOM Image Compression Alternative Using Huffman Coding." 2019, Journal of Healthcare Engineering, Volume, Article ID 5810540, 11 pages <https://doi.org/10.1155/2019/5810540>
6. Shakir, H. R (2019), "An image encryption method based on selective AES coding of wavelet transform and chaotic pixel shuffling." Multimedia Tools and Applications, 78(18), 26073-26087
7. Nematzadeh, H., Enayatifar, R., Motameni, H., Guimarães, F. G., & Coelho, V.N (2018), "Medical image encryption using a hybrid model of modified genetic algorithm and coupled map lattices." Optics and Lasers in Engineering, 110, 24- 32.
8. G. R. W. Thoms R. Muresan and A. Al-Dweik (2019), "Chaotic Encryption Algorithm With Key Controlled Neural Networks for Intelligent Transportation Systems," IEEE Access, vol. 7, pp. 158697-158709
9. Raja Masadeh, Basel A. Mahafzah and Ahmad Sharieh (2019), "Sea Lion Optimization Algorithm", International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications(IJACSA), vol. 10, no.5.
10. Koppu, S. & Viswanatham, V. M (2018), "Medical image security enhancement using two dimensional chaotic mapping optimized by self- adaptive grey wolf algorithm" Evolutionary Intelligence, 11(1), 53-71.
11. Seyedali Mirjalili, Andrew Lewisa (2016), "The Whale Optimization Algorithm", Advances in Engineering Software, vol. 95, pp. 51-67.
12. Mirjalili S, Mirjalili SM, Lewis A (2014) Grey wolf optimizer. Adv Eng Softw 69:46–61.
13. Abdullah AH, Enayatifar R, Leeb M (2012), "A hybrid genetic algorithm and chaotic function model for image encryption." Int J Electron Commun (AEU) 66:806–816